

IMPROVING VIDEO CONTENT METADATA THROUGH ADDITION OF AI GENERATED SUMMARIES

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Abstract – This poster outlines the development and implementation of a Python script designed to enhance the descriptive metadata of video files ingested into the digital preservation system, Preservica. The script utilizes advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques to generate summaries from video content and updates the metadata accordingly.

Keywords – Metadata Extraction, Ingest, Audiovisual Content, AI, Preservica.

Conference Topics – Tūtaki – Encounter.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of digital preservation, the accurate and detailed description of stored content is crucial for effective retrieval and management. Preservica, a widely used digital preservation system, has been used to ingest terabytes of video files in our organization that currently lack descriptive metadata beyond their titles. This limitation hampers the ability to search and utilize these video files effectively, further complicating the management and retrieval of valuable information.

II. PROBLEM ANALYSES

The primary issue at hand is the existence of numerous terabytes of video files in our digital repository with minimal descriptive metadata. The Preservica system currently lacks functionality to

extract metadata from the existing content. This absence of detailed metadata restricts the usability and accessibility of these files, making it challenging for users to locate and identify relevant content. This problem necessitates a solution that can automatically generate and update descriptive metadata for the video files.

III. TECHNICAL RESOURCES

To address the problem, a Python script was written with the following technical resources:

1. **OpenAI Whisper Model:** Used for transcribing the audio content of video files.
2. **Tiktoken:** Employed for tokenization of the transcriptions.
3. **ChatGPT-4o:** Utilized for summarizing the transcribed content.
4. **pyPreservica library:** Used for updating the metadata in Preservica.
5. **Python Language:** The script was written in Python to leverage its extensive libraries and ease of integration.

IV. SOLUTION

The solution employs a multi-step process for summarizing video files and updating their metadata within Preservica. Due to the sensitive nature of the

content, OpenAI Whisper models and essential libraries are deployed on-premises. Additionally, our private instance of ChatGPT-4o on-premises is utilized. The following outlines the required parameters and workflow steps:

Parameters:

- Reference ID of the video files root folder in Preservica.
- Path of video files in a local or NAS folder.
- Credentials to access Preservica.
- Prompt required for ChatGPT-4o summarization.

Process Steps:

1. **Transcription:** Video files are transcribed using the OpenAI Whisper model.
2. **Tokenization:** The transcriptions are tokenized using Tiktoken.
3. **Chunking:** If the tokenized content exceeds the maximum number of tokens accepted by ChatGPT-4o, it is divided into manageable chunks.
4. **Summarization:** The tokenized content is sent to ChatGPT-4o for summarization via API calls.
5. **Metadata Update:** The generated summary is uploaded to Preservica using the pyPreservica library.

This approach adds useful metadata to the description field of video files in Preservica, improving their accessibility and usability. Below is a sample summary:

The conversation covers a wide range of topics, including the importance of regular communication and updates, with a commitment to quarterly meetings. Participants discuss the unpredictability of global trade flows and the need to prepare for various future scenarios, particularly in agriculture, where feeding an additional three billion people requires doubling trade...
 *** This description was generated by AI based on the transcript of the video recording ***

V. WORKFLOW DIAGRAM

VI. REFERENCES

Whisper: <https://github.com/openai/whisper>

Tiktoken: <https://github.com/openai/tiktoken>

pyPreservica: <https://pypreservica.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Elvis Valdes Ramirez is an IT Analyst at the World Bank Group Archives and Records section. He has worked as a software developer for many years and has been the administrator of the digital preservation system Preservica for the last 10 years.

